

Editing Benedictus Polonus

Textual Cruces and Editorial Principles in the *Relatio*

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Abstract

This article accompanies my edition of Benedictus Polonus's *Relatio* (Zenodo, 2025), an oral-derived eyewitness account of the 1245-1247 Franciscan mission to the Quriltai of Güyük Khan. To make my editing-process more transparent, I will examine three textual cruces where editorial decisions affect historical interpretation: the left-behind friar (§2), some legendary peoples including Cynocephali and Parocitae (§7), and Benedict's rendering of the throne platform (§10). I will also shortly discuss the evidence of the Cologne chronicle for the oral background of Benedict's text and the editorial principles that I applied in the edition: These are a) respect for the transmitted text, b) annotation over emendation, and c) reading the report alongside Carpini rather than against him.

Keywords: *Benedictus Polonus, Mongol Empire, Textual criticism, Oral transmission, Franciscan missions, Editing*

1. Introduction

The annotated edition of Benedictus Polonus's *Relatio* (deposited on Zenodo in November 2025) is the first complete historical-literal translation of this text into English and the first newly annotated Latin edition since Anastasius van den Wyngaert's *Sinica Franciscana* of 1929.¹ One might reasonably ask what documentation an edition of such a brief work (barely nine pages in Wyngaert's printing) really requires? The answer, as it seems to me, lies in the nature of this short text itself. The *Relatio* is not a straightforward composition by a traveler or author of any kind. It is the product of an oral report, delivered by a tired friar passing through Cologne in the autumn of 1247, where it was transcribed by a learned scribe whose name we do not know. There is no evidence of authorial revision or a second redaction comparable to Carpini's expansion in chapter nine. It seems the text was fixed at or at most shortly after the moment of its transcription at Cologne. After this, it circulated as a stable component of the Carpini mission corpus. Many of the editorial decisions that shape the Zenodo edition emerge from this somewhat hybrid origin.

I should state at the outset what this article is not meant to be: It is not a biographical study of Benedictus Polonus. That work has been ably undertaken elsewhere, most recently in a concise and very useful overview that establishes the known facts of Benedictus's life and his role as interpreter for the Carpini mission.² Therefore, this article has a different focus: the philological and editorial problems that any future scholar working on the *Relatio* must confront. My goal is to document and to make transparent the choices that shaped the edition.

The *Relatio* presents unusual challenges for any editor. Unlike Carpini's *Ystoria Mongalorum*, which has a more complex tradition of multiple recensions and revisions, the *Relatio* came to us in a small and quite stable group of manuscripts, which are represented by the Vienna and Paris witnesses.³ Its textual difficulties stem not so much from competing versions but from its specific genesis as a text between oral narration and written record. Benedictus delivered his account at Cologne in the autumn of 1247, speaking in what the contemporary Cologne chronicle describes as "viva voce et dilucide" ("with lively voice and clear").⁴ This for any European listener surely exciting spoken report was then transcribed by an unnamed scribe, identified only as a "prelato et quondam scholastico Coloniensi, hystoriarum non ignaro" ("a prelate and former scholastic of Cologne, not ignorant of histories"), and added to a "libellus specialis" ("specific little book")

1 Benedictus Polonus, *The Relatio of Benedictus Polonus: An Annotated Edition and Historical-Literal Translation*, Version 3.0, ed. Gregor Werner (Zenodo, November 9, 2025), <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18609217>

2 Czekalska, Renata. "The Journey of Benedictus Polonus or a European Discovery of Asia before Marco Polo," in *Acta Via Serica* 4, no. 2 (2019), 79-95.

3 On the two redactions of Carpini's *Ystoria*, see Gregor Werner, *Die militärische Macht der Mongolen in den Berichten der Carpinimission: Die Unterschiede in der Darstellung bei Carpini und C. de Bridia* (PhD diss., FernUniversität Hagen, 2011/2012), 13 (footnote 36), <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17606979>. On the two redactions of Carpini's *Ystoria*, see the discussion in Wyngaert's introduction to his edition John of Plano Carpini. *Ystoria Mongalorum*. In *Sinica Franciscana*, Vol. I: *Itinera et relationes fratrum minorum saeculi XIII et XIV*, edited by Anastasius van den Wyngaert, 3-130. Quaracchi, Florence: Collegium S. Bonaventurae, 1929, esp. 9-13, which establishes the manuscript tradition and the relationship between the different versions. For Benedictus's textual stability see Wyngaert's introduction to his edition: Benedictus Polonus, *Relatio*, in *Sinica Franciscana I: Itinera et Relationes Fratrum Minorum Saeculi XIII et XIV*, ed. Anastasius van den Wyngaert (Quaracchi: Collegium S. Bonaventurae, 1929), 133-134.

4 *Annales Sancti Pantaleonis Coloniensis*, quoted in Alf Önnersfors, ed., *Hystoria Tartarorum C. de Bridia Monachi* (Berlin: Walter de Gruyter, 1967), V.

concerning the Tartars.⁵ What we read today is, therefore, a collaborative text: Benedictus's eyewitness memory, filtered through the Latin literacy and learned categories of an anonymous clerical scribe.

Such a hybrid origin raises several editorial questions that differ from those we encounter when approaching Carpini's *Ystoria*. While Carpini can be edited as a text written by one specific author, comparing the redactions to recover his final intentions (or at least try), the *Relatio* demands a different approach. Any editor must ask continuously what in the text belongs to Benedictus and what to the scribe who gave his spoken words Latin literary form. And rarely (as any close reader will find), the answer is straightforward. Actually, in most cases it could not be said with certainty. In the editorial principles of the Zenodo edition, I therefore emphasize restraint: I emended sparingly, annotated rather generously, and mostly tried to preserve the transmitted text; even where it appeared somewhat awkward or contradictory. The goal was not to produce a smooth, "corrected" version but to present the text as it survived, with all the textures and tensions that reveal its origins in a specific moment of cross-cultural encounter and oral-written co-creation. With this approach I followed mostly Wyngaert's original attitude.

To make the decisions and the overall approach to textual purity more clear, I focus on three textual cruces as examples where editorial decisions have significant consequences for the historical interpretation. The first concerns the left-behind friar mentioned in §2 of the *Relatio*; a passage that, when it is read alongside Carpini, shows us the different perspectives of the two Franciscan observers. The second examines the list of legendary peoples in §7, where Benedictus (or his scribe) includes *Cynocephali* and mouthless *Parocitae* among the nations that were conquered by the Mongols. In the third, we will look at the word *tabulatum* in §10, where Benedictus describes Güyük Khan's throne platform within the *Sira Orda*; a term that Carpini uses elsewhere to describe a wooden fence, revealing the ambiguity of medieval Latin when confronted with unfamiliar material culture. The external evidence of the Cologne chronicle and its implications for understanding the *Relatio* as an oral-derived text are the topic of a fourth section. The short article will conclude with the editorial principles that guided the edition and a brief speculation about future research.

2. The Text and Its Transmission

Before examining specific textual cruces, we should establish the nature of the text itself and the circumstances of its transmission. The *Relatio* is a short work, occupying only roughly nine pages in Wyngaert's edition, and it covers the entire two-year journey of the Carpini mission from Lyon to the Mongol court and back. Unlike Carpini's *Ystoria*, which is organized thematically into chapters on Mongol geography, customs, religion, military organization, and defense against the enemy, the *Relatio* all in all follows a chronological structure, narrating the journey as a sequence of encounters with Mongol officials, subject peoples, and the imperial court itself.

The sole external witness to the text's genesis is the passage from the *Annales Sancti Pantaleonis Coloniensis* already quoted above. This chronicle entry, which Önnorfors printed in full in his

5 Önnorfors, *Hystoria Tartarorum*, V.

introduction to C. de Bridia's *Hystoria Tartarorum*, provides the necessary background information for understanding what the *Relatio* is and how it came to be. The relevant section reads:

“unus eorundem fratrum Minorum, Benedictus nomine, Polonus genere, sicut vidit et audivit, cuidam prelato et quondam scholastico Coloniensi, hystoriarum non ignaro, cum transitum per Coloniam faceret, viva voce et dilucide explanavit, que libello speciali, quem iidem fratres de ortu et ritu ceterisque circumstantiis Tartarorum retulerunt, ipso fratre oretenus singula declarante, sunt adiecta.”⁶ (“One of these Friars Minor, Benedict by name, a Pole by birth, just as he saw and heard, explained with lively voice and clear to a certain prelate and former schoolmaster of Cologne, not ignorant of histories, when he was passing through Cologne, and these things were added to a special little book, which the same brothers brought back concerning the origin and customs and other circumstances of the Tartars, with the brother himself narrating each aspect orally.”)

Several features of this passage deserve a closer look: First, the chronicler twice stresses the orality of the transmission: “viva voce et dilucide explanavit” and again “oretenus singula declarante.” The repetition is deliberate, I think. It signals to the reader that this is not a text that was composed in writing but a spoken report that was transcribed. Second, the scribe is characterized in terms that suggest learned competence. He is a “prelatus” and a former “scholasticus”, and he is “hystoriarum non ignarus” (“not ignorant of histories”). This is not a passive stenographer jotting down notes or taking dictation, but we should imagine him as a fully literate figure. He must have, to a certain extent, been capable of shaping oral testimony into fitting Latin form. Third, the chronicler says that Benedictus’s account was “adiecta” (“added”) to an existing “libellus specialis” (“specific booklet”) that the friars had brought back concerning the Mongols. This suggests that the *Relatio* was right from the start conceived as supplementary material by some; a spoken appendix to a written analytical report.⁷ It appears the text was fixed at or shortly after the moment of its transcription at Cologne, and it circulated thereafter as a stable, if minor, component of the Carpini mission corpus. This somewhat minor status in the mission’s context should not be mistaken for a lack of importance, however. I think closer inspection shows that there are enough unique features in this small text that give it independent importance as a witness.

For an editor, this history of transmission has direct consequences. There is no authorial manuscript to reconstruct, no real competing versions to decide on (apart from slight differences in the mss tradition). The editorial task is therefore not to recover a highly uncertain *Urtext* but to present the transmitted text clearly and to annotate its difficulties.

3. First Textual Crux: The Left-Behind Friar

The first crux appears early in the *Relatio*, in the section describing the mission’s initial encounter with Mongol authorities on the outward journey. Benedictus tells that after crossing the Dnieper River and proceeding into the steppe, the party reached the first Mongol guard post. There, one of their group was left behind.

⁶ Önnersfors, *Hystoria Tartarorum*, V, lines 3-14.

⁷ This might be a bit too harsh for this text, that contains unique snippets of information that do not appear in Carpini.

The Latin reads: “tercio fratre debilitato, cum equis et clientulis quos secum adduxerant ibidem relictis.”⁸ (“the third brother having been weakened, with the horses and attendants, which they had brought with them, left behind in that place.”) Grammatically the phrase is straightforward, but its historical referent is not immediately clear. Who was this “tercius frater”? And how does this abandonment relate to the other references to left-behind friars in the Carpini corpus?

The relationship between these passages, i.e., Benedictus §2, Carpini’s prologue, Carpini IX 46, and C. de Bridia’s opening, requires careful disentanglement. Sure, we could simply harmonize these different hints and identify the “tercius frater” of Benedictus with the “socii et servientes” of Carpini IX 46 and ultimately with C. de Bridia’s Ceslaus. But, I think, the chronology does not support this simple identification. If we go through this conundrum with a fine comb, we see that Benedictus places the abandonment at the first Mongol guard post, before the party reached Batu’s camp. Carpini’s prologue, however, gives no name for any third companion; it names only himself and Benedictus.⁹ And the “socii et servientes” of IX 46 were detained at Batu’s camp (or earlier) and reunited only at Maucy, a location the mission reached on the return journey after passing through several guard posts.¹⁰

C. de Bridia, writing at second hand, provides a name for this (or another?) figure: “Ceslaus.” However, the fact that this name appears only in C. de Bridia’s derivative account, and is absent from the direct witnesses of Benedictus and Carpini, complicates any attempt to assign a definitive name to the “tercius frater.” The *Relatio* tells us only of the event, not the name. The editorial decision in the Zenodo edition was therefore to retain Wyngaert’s reading without emendation but to annotate the passage to clarify these complexities. The text stands as transmitted; the annotation provides the reader with the tools to navigate the discrepancies without imposing a false harmonization. I think we can carefully dare to identify the “tercius frater” with the Ceslaus named by C. de Bridia. But we can not be sure at this point.

Important to note is, however, that the abandonment occurs at a different stage of the journey than the detention mentioned in Carpini IX 46. The two accounts are complementary, not contradictory. Benedictus provides detail about the outward journey; Carpini provides context about the return journey that Benedictus just implies. C. de Bridia, writing from the oral reports of the returning friars, adds yet another layer of mediation. It is fascinating to see how the naming of the figure in C. de Bridia, contrasted with the anonymity in Benedictus and Carpini, gives us a live example of the oral chain through which his account was transmitted.

4. Second Textual Crux: The Cynocephali and Parocitae

The second crux appears in §7 of the *Relatio*, where Benedictus provides a catalogue of the peoples subject to Mongol rule. The list includes historical nations, i.e., Alans, Georgians, Circassians, Khazars, and figures drawn from the legendary ethnography of the classical and medieval

8 Benedictus Polonus (ed. Wyngaert), *Relatio*, §2, 135.

9 Carpini, *Ystoria*, Prologus §3 (ed. Wyngaert): “...tam nos quam frater Benedictus Polonus eiusdem Ordinis, qui nostre tribulationis fuit socius et interpres, fecimus studiose.”

10 Carpini, *Ystoria*, IX 46: “Et inde venimus usque ad Maucy in sabbato infra octavam pentecostes, ubi erant nostri socii et servientes, qui erant retenti, quos ad nos reduci fecimus.” The reunion at Maucy occurs on the return journey, after the mission had left the imperial court and passed back through the Mongol guard system. The “socii et servientes” were therefore detained at some point during the outward journey, maybe at or before Batu’s camp or one of the intervening guard posts, and were only released when the returning party reached Maucy.

traditions. Among those are the “Cynocephali” (dog-headed men) and the “Parocitae”, who are being described as follows: “... Parocitas qui habent os parvum et angustum, nec quidquam possunt masticare, sed sorbicia sumunt et vaporibus carniū et fructuum reficiuntur.”¹¹ (“... the Parocitae, who have a tiny and narrow mouth and cannot chew anything, but consume “suckable” foods and live on the vapors of meat and fruit.”)

The presence of such (for the modern reader) obviously legendary material in an otherwise factual report poses another dilemma. Should the text be emended to remove what could be seen as an interpolation? Should it be retained but marked as false? Or should it be treated as integral to the text and annotated accordingly?

This edition, as did Wyngaert, adopts the third approach. The passage is therefore retained as it was transmitted, and the annotation traces the sources of the legendary material. The “Cynocephali” are a commonplace of classical ethnography, appearing in Pliny’s *Natural History* and Solinus’s *Collectanea Rerum Memorabilium* as inhabitants of India or Scythia. The “Parocitae” (also spelled “Parositae”) come from a similar tradition, though their precise origin is much more obscure. They appear in the medieval bestiary tradition and in encyclopedic works such as Isidore of Seville’s *Etymologiae*.¹²

When medieval observers encountered unfamiliar phenomena, they processed that information through their own cultural categories. The result was not simple error but a form of cognitive-categorical translation: the unfamiliar was assimilated to the known, even when the fit was imperfect (in how far it was imperfect to the era is debatable though). The goal was to harmonize the unknown with the known. In the case of the *Relatio*, the inclusion of “Cynocephali” and “Parocitae” is itself historical evidence. It shows what a learned thirteenth-century European (whether Benedictus himself or, more likely, the Cologne scribe) considered plausible ethnography. Therefore, I concluded, that to delete the passage would be to erase that evidence, even when it is not clear if Benedict or the scribe are the origin of these mythical peoples.

A comparison with Carpini is instructive here. Carpini’s *Ystoria* also contains legendary material. But his treatment of such material differs from Benedict’s in tone and framing. Carpini tends to distance himself from the more extravagant claims, using qualifying phrases such as “ut dicitur” (“as it is said”) or “nobis dicebatur” (“it was said to us”). Benedictus, by contrast, presents the list of peoples as straightforward fact, without much qualification. The difference may reflect the

11 Benedictus Polonus (ed. Werner), *Relatio*, §7.

12 The “Cynocephali” and “Parocitae” belong to a well-established tradition of monstrous races found in classical and medieval encyclopedias and cartography. For the tradition as a whole, and for its depiction in missionary and pilgrimage contexts, see John Block Friedman, *The Monstrous Races in Medieval Art and Thought* (Cambridge, MA: Harvard University Press, 1981), 79–86. For the persistence of monstrous races in travel literature, and for the tension between empirical observation and inherited tradition, see Peter Jackson, *The Mongols and the West, 1221–1410* (Abingdon: Routledge, 2005), 154. Jackson notes that even the Franciscans, who sought rational explanations remained “... creatures of their time, and if they found no evidence for a phenomenon that was part of the common stock of Western folklore, their reaction was often simply to relegate it beyond their now dramatically extended geographical horizons.”

mediating role of the respective scribe. Carpini wrote and revised his own text; Benedictus spoke, and a learned scribe (“hystoriarum non ignarus”) gave his words literary form.¹³

The scribe, steeped in the above-mentioned encyclopedic tradition, may have recognized the names of the Alans and Georgians as historical and might have felt the need to add the “Cynocephali” and “Parocitae” from his own store of learning. Alternatively, Benedictus himself may have reported what he had heard as fact, and the scribe simply transcribed it. The scarce evidence we have does not allow us to decide between these possibilities. Assuming that they too must inhabit the vast and poorly mapped spaces of the Mongol Empire probably was not influenced by a wish to add exoticism. He might have felt that what was known from the revered ancient authors should be added because it was surely factual. Not adding it would have seemed like the report was unreliable since everyone *knew* these people were there and therefore must have been encountered by the friars.

The editorial principle here is, once again, annotation over emendation. The legendary material is retained, but the reader is given the tools to understand its origin and its function within the text. After all, the *Relatio* is not modern ethnography. It is a thirteenth-century report shaped by the categories and expectations of its moment. To read it well, we must see those categories clearly, not erase them.

5. Third Textual Crux: *Tabulatum* — Fence, Platform, or Both?

The third crux arises from a single Latin word that appears in two of the three accounts of the 1246 *quriltai*: *tabulatum*. The word itself is not problematic in isolation; it is a standard medieval Latin term derived from *tabula* (“plank” or “board”), meaning broadly “something made of planks or boards.” The real crux, I think, lies in how two different observers, describing the same ceremonial complex, used the same word to refer to two entirely different structures.

The word appears in the *Relatio* at §10, in Benedictus’s description of Güyük Khan’s throne within the *Sira Orda*, the imperial “Yellow/ Golden Tent.” The passage reads:

“... viderunt ipsum coronatum, in mirifico habitu effulgentem, sedentem in medio tentorii super quoddam tabulatum, auro et argento multipliciter decoratum et desuper cancellatum, super quod quatuor distinctionibus ascensuum per gradus ascendebatur.”¹⁴
 (“... they saw him crowned, resplendent in wondrous attire, sitting in the middle of the tent upon a certain platform richly adorned with gold and silver and enclosed from above by railings, which one ascended by four distinct stepped approaches.”)

Here, *tabulatum* clearly refers to a raised wooden platform or dais, a structure that supported the Great Khan’s throne and elevated him above his subjects. The important phrases are “in medio tentorii” (“in the middle of the tent”) and the description of the four stairways (“quatuor distinctionibus ascensuum per gradus”), which only make sense if the structure required a form of ascent. The platform was decorated with gold and silver, had railings above (“cancellatum”), and each of its four stairways was reserved for another social group: the central stair for the Khan alone,

13 Granted, we can assume that Benedict had another look at what was written down.

14 Benedictus Polonus (ed. Werner), *Relatio* §10.

the two stairs at the side for nobles and those of middle rank, and a fourth one behind for the Empress Mother, the Empress, and the Khan's immediate kinsmen.¹⁵

The same word, however, appears in Carpini's *Ystoria Mongalorum* with a different meaning. In Carpini's description of the *Sira Orda* at Töregene's court where the preliminary ceremonies of the enthronement took place he writes: "Et in circuitu erat factum ligneum tabulatum, quod variis ymaginibus erat depictum."¹⁶ ("And around was erected a wooden fence, which was painted with various depictions")

Here, "tabulatum" refers to a wooden enclosure or fence ("ligneum tabulatum") that surrounded the tent. The words, we should focus on here, are "in circuitu" ("around it"). Carpini is describing the perimeter of the ceremonial space, a structure that enclosed the tent to regulate access to the center of power and was decorated with painted images. Its function was obviously twofold, i.e., spatial and ceremonial: it marked the boundary between the inner (sacred) space and the outer world.

The interpretive challenge, therefore, seems this: one word appears in two tightly connected texts, yet, with two different meanings. Carpini and Benedictus both used "tabulatum" because the word was broad enough to cover both meanings. A structure made of planks could be either a fence or a platform. But the two observers were describing quite different elements within the same ceremonial complex. Carpini's "tabulatum" was "in circuitu", i.e., around the tent; Benedictus's was "in medio tentorii," i.e., in the middle of the tent. Carpini's was an enclosure; Benedictus's was a dais. The same Latin word, applied to two different structures, reveals the multivalence of medieval Latin vocabulary, especially when the speaker was confronted with unfamiliar material culture.

Why does this distinction matter, one might ask. But indeed, the choice of translation affects how we understand the *quriltai* and its material culture. If Carpini's "tabulatum" is a fence, it indicates that access to the *Sira Orda* was controlled and regulated. The painted images on the enclosure suggest that even the boundary itself carried symbolic meaning. It becomes clear, that the fence was not merely functional but ceremonial. It was a visual statement of Mongol power and a mechanism of control. If Benedictus's "tabulatum," in contrast, is a platform, it indicates that the Khan's authority was materially represented through elevation. He sat above his subjects, and the four stairways encoded a specific form of hierarchy in architecture. The platform became a political statement about who could approach the Khan, and from which direction.

Both readings are valid in context. They are not contradictory at all but complementary. Carpini, the strategist, saw the fence and might have understood it as a mechanism of control over access. Benedictus, the eyewitness, saw the platform and understood it as a mechanism of hierarchy and ritual ordering. Both were right. They observed the same ceremonial logic from different angles: the Mongols used material structures to project power. The difference in both accounts reflects their

15 The four stairways are described in the same passage: "Et tres quidem ascensus erant anterieus ad tabulatum, per quorum medium solus Imperator ascendebat et descendebat, per reliquos duos collaterales potentes et mediocres, per quartum vero, qui erat a dorso eius, mater et uxor sua et consanguinei ascendebant." ("There were three approaches before the platform: through the central one, only the Emperor ascended and descended; through the other two flanking ones, the powerful and those of middle rank; through the fourth however, which was behind him, his mother and wife, and kinsmen ascended.") The architectural arrangement encodes Mongol social hierarchy in physical form.

16 John of Plano Carpini, *Ystoria Mongalorum* IX 29. The phrase "ligneum tabulatum" clearly means a wooden structure made of planks; the context ("in circuitu") determines that it is an enclosure, not a platform.

distinct observational lenses, not any error in reporting. Carpini's text was composed for the papal curia, which needed actionable intelligence about Mongol military and political structures; he therefore emphasized the mechanisms of control. Benedictus's text, on the other hand, was delivered orally to a learned audience in Cologne; he therefore might have felt it fitting to emphasize the visual and hierarchical spectacle of the enthronement. The divergence in their use of "tabulatum" consequently reflects not only the semantic range of the Latin word but also the different purposes and audiences of the two texts.

The crux is, in the end, interpretive due to the many meanings of the Latin word and the different contexts in which it was used. This is a common challenge in editing ancient or medieval texts, where the same word can mean different things in different contexts. Translating "tabulatum" uniformly as "platform" or "fence" would be a clear error; the context must guide the translation.

The logical solution was therefore to translate Benedictus's "tabulatum" as "platform." The decision is based on the context, the four stairways, the decoration, and the parallel usage with different meaning in Carpini and Benedict.

6. The Cologne Chronicle and the Question of Orality

The external evidence of the Cologne chronicle, quoted in Section 2 above, provides the essential background for understanding the *Relatio* as an originally oral text. The chronicler's emphasis on "viva voce" could be ignored by a superficial reading, but it is actually rather significant. In thirteenth-century chronicles, oral testimony was often highly valued, in some contexts more than written documents; the origin from an eyewitness gave it credibility, that otherwise only old revered authorship guaranteed. But the chronicle also raises questions that are directly influencing editorial practice. Who was the "prelatus et quondam scholasticus" who transcribed Benedictus's words? What did he add or reshape? And how should we approach a text that, in the end, is a collaboration between narrator and scribe?

The chronicle offers only a few further clues. The scribe was not a nobody but a prelate, which suggests a person of some standing in the Cologne church, perhaps a canon of the cathedral or a senior cleric who was in some capacity attached to the episcopal court. He was a former "scholasticus", a term that in that era likely meant a master of the cathedral school, responsible for the education of the clergy. And he was "hystoriarum non ignarus". This last phrase is significant. From it, we learn that the scribe was not just literate but learned and obviously familiar with the traditions that shaped medieval understandings of the world. He was, that seems certain, the kind of person who would know about "Cynocephali" and "Parocitae".

It is rather clear now, we cannot assume that every word of the *Relatio* originated with Benedictus. The learned scribe likely shaped the oral report in at least three ways: First, he gave it proper Latin form, correcting grammatical irregularities and imposing the rhythms of literate prose.¹⁷ Second, he

17 For a parallel example of a trained Latinist shaping a text through the use of rhythmic prose cadences, see Alf Önnersfors's analysis of the "cursus" in his introduction to C. de Bridia's *Hystoria Tartarorum* IX. Önnersfors notes that C. de Bridia was "haudquaquam imperitus" ("by no means unskilled") in its use, and that more than three-quarters of his sentences are "bound by the *cursus*," i.e. the medieval *ars dictaminis*. He also argues that the text's medieval Latin features should be "explained, not corrected," and that Carpini should not be used as a model for

may have even supplemented Benedictus's account with material from his own learning, i.e., the classical ethnography of Pliny and Solinus, and the biblical and apocalyptic patterns that structured European expectations at this time. Third, we cannot exclude that he omitted or compressed material that seemed irrelevant or redundant, thereby focusing the account on what he saw as most significant.

However, I want to emphasize that Benedict's oral delivery does not imply illiteracy. As a Franciscan friar and interpreter for a papal mission, he almost certainly possessed Latin literacy. But the context of his short stop in Cologne, likely favored an oral report over a written composition. After all, he was exhausted from the long journey. The scribe's role thus probably was not to compensate for Benedict's inability in any area but to provide the polished Latin that a written text required.

So what does that mean for the decisions made in the process of editing? The editorial response should not be to strip away the scribal layer hoping to recover an assumed *pure* Benedictine original. On the contrary, we should accept that layer as integral to the text as it survives. The proper response therefore must be transparency: to annotate passages where scribal intervention seems likely, to note parallels with classical and medieval sources, and to acknowledge the collaborative nature of the text. Consequently, this edition aimed to follow that approach throughout.

7. Applied Editorial Principles

With the three textual cruces examined above, i.e., the left-behind friar, the legendary peoples, and the question of how to render specific technical words, I hope to have sufficiently illustrated a consistent set of editorial principles. I think it is useful to state these principles explicitly, as documentation for users of the edition and as a contribution to the broader discussion of how oral-derived medieval texts could and should be edited.

Principle 1: Respect for the transmitted text

The edition emends only where the reading is clearly impossible; a severe scribal error, a grammatical impossibility, or maybe a lacuna that makes the passage unintelligible. In any other case, whenever the transmitted text is just awkward or apparently contradictory, it is retained and annotated. My goal was not to produce a smooth, *corrected* version but to present the text as it survives.

Principle 2: Transparency about scribal mediation

The edition acknowledges that the *Relatio* is not a pure authorial original but the product of narration and transcription. Annotations indicate where scribal shaping likely took place. That might have happened in the form of classical or biblical or formulaic phrasing, or the imposition of literate structures on spoken content.

Principle 3: Annotation over emendation

emendation (X).

Whenever the text presents difficulties, the edition provides annotation rather than emending the text: legendary material, apparent contradictions, etc. The annotation supplies the reader with, hopefully, sufficient tools to navigate the difficulty without falling for a false resolution.

Principle 4: Read alongside Carpini, not against him

The *Relatio* and the *Ystoria* are complementary accounts of the same mission. Differences between them should, however, not be interpreted as errors but evidence of different perspectives or priorities; and certainly of different moments of composition. In this edition, I therefore did intentionally not collate the two texts in any systematically way. My goal was to provide the foundation for such comparative reading by presenting the *Relatio* in a reliable, annotated form.

Principle 5: The translation as interpretation

The connected English translation aims for historical-literal accuracy. It preserves the texture of the Latin even where this produces slightly awkward English, and it renders technical terms consistently. Thus, the translation is not a freestanding work but an integral part of the edition, designed to make the text accessible while remaining as close as possible to the original.

These principles reflect my broader editorial philosophy. One could describe it as documentary rather than aiming for reconstructive classical purity. The edition does not attempt to recover a lost original behind the surviving manuscripts. It presents the text as it has been transmitted, with all the tensions and occasional strangeness that reveal its origin in a specific moment of cross-cultural encounter and oral reportage.

8. Conclusion

The *Relatio* of Benedictus Polonus is a small text, and thus easily overshadowed by Carpini's much heftier *Ystoria* and in general by the large corpus of thirteenth-century Mongol mission literature. But its brevity and unusual genesis make it a valuable example of how medieval textual transmission worked. The *Relatio* sheds light on a process through which the raw information of the journey was shaped into the textual form that reached the European public and, eventually, us.

I want to suggest the editorial principles applied in my edition (and they are certainly widely used) can be a functional model for editing similar oral-derived texts. Granted, they do not solve every difficulty. They do, however, provide a consistent framework for presenting the *Relatio* and similar texts to modern readers.

Future research on Benedictus Polonus might proceed in several directions. The identity of the Cologne scribe, the "prelato et quondam scholastico Coloniensi," remains an open question. Further research in the records of the Cologne cathedral chapter might give us a name one day. Also, the relationship between the *Relatio* and C. de Bridia's *Historia Tartarorum*, both of which derive from the oral reports of the returned friars, surely could yield an exciting comparative study. This companion article together with the edition, I hope, serve as the scholarly infrastructure for that future work. If the edition enables other scholars to read Benedictus Polonus more clearly, and to pursue the questions that his brief but vivid report continues to raise, it will have served its purpose.

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